

Assessing and Improving Teaching Space Utilization for Operational Efficiency: A Study in a Ghanaian Tertiary Institution

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Abstract

The issue of inadequate teaching space facilities in tertiary institutions in Ghana could be addressed through efficient utilization of existing facilities. Underutilized teaching space facilities can result in unnecessary institutional costs. Therefore, management needs to rigorously assess how their physical teaching spaces are being utilized, rather than simply assuming they are insufficient. This article aims to assess the utilization of physical teaching space facilities and explore measures for efficient utilization. The study is grounded in facility management theory, adopting a convergent parallel mixed-method design anchored in pragmatic philosophical assumptions. The population for the study consists of 9 academic administrators who are involved in matters relating to teaching space facilities and 26 general-purpose lecture rooms. A purposive sampling technique was utilized to select the nine (9) academic administrators, while a census sampling technique was used to select all the 26 general-purpose lecture rooms. Observation checklists and interview guides were utilized for data collection. Data were analyzed using descriptive analysis and thematic analysis techniques. The study found that general-purpose lecture rooms achieved a low Global Utilization Rate (GUR) of 41.5%, indicating underutilization of the lecture facility. The study further revealed the role of proper planning and coordination in achieving efficient space utilization. The study recommends that management revise its academic timetables to achieve a more balanced distribution of classes and also provide additional facilities to prevent overcrowding, ensuring adequate space for all students.

Keywords: *Efficiency, Facility, Infrastructure, Management, Teaching Space, Utilization Rate.*

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Introduction

The quality of education in an institution is intricately tied to the accessibility and efficient use of teaching space facilities. Teaching space facilities refer to the physical or virtual environments created to enhance teaching and learning activities. These facilities encompass various spaces, including lecture rooms, laboratories, libraries, auditoriums, and many others. In the pursuit of quality education, it is imperative to not only expand teaching facilities but also to optimize its utilization for the benefit of students. This suggests that facility utilization should be a top priority for every educational management. Ademola, Olufemi, and Chukwuemeka (2018) point out that the efficient utilization of institutional resources such as teaching space facilities at the college or university level has yet to be satisfactorily achieved, particularly due to a low level of efficiency in aspects such as ineffective scheduling of classes, design and layout of teaching spaces, inadequate resource allocation, and inefficiency in the adaptability of teaching spaces hampers their capacity to accommodate diverse teaching methods and evolving educational practices. The success of a tertiary educational institution in achieving its goals, which include fostering academic success among students, is linked to the efficient utilization of educational resources. Thus, efficient educational resource utilization forms part of the indicators used to determine the success of an institutional programme (Usman, 2016).

The current teaching facilities at public tertiary institutions in Ghana are under strain due to a lack of infrastructure, particularly teaching space facilities, as a result of the rise in student enrolment without a commensurate allocation of educational resources (Sephania et al., 2017). Due to the lack of infrastructure in almost all of Ghana's public higher educational institutions, only a small percentage of eligible candidates are accepted into public tertiary education, and many eligible Ghanaian students are turned away (Quansah, 2015). The Vice-Chancellor of UDS, in his speech at the 30th Matriculation Ceremony, acknowledged the remarkable rise in student enrolment over the past five years, attributing it to the success of the Free Senior High School (FSHS) Programme. During the matriculation ceremony, which serves as the university management's official welcome of the admitted students, the Vice-Chancellor mentioned that the admission for the 2021/2022 academic year at the University was partly influenced by the university's infrastructure deficiency, resulting in many qualified applicants being denied admission to various programmes at the university (University for Development Studies, 2022b).

Akin, the Vice-Chancellor of UDS, in his speech at the 23rd Congregation Ceremony, highlighted the need for the university to revamp its infrastructure to accommodate the growing number of students seeking admission (University for Development Studies, 2022a). As a result, the management of the University for Development Studies (UDS) has been focusing on expanding educational facilities, including lecture halls, laboratories, accommodations, library facilities and internet services, on its campuses over the past few years. However, the university's request for expanding infrastructure, particularly the teaching space facilities, lacks sufficient scientific evidence to support their request. This is because there has not been any cited survey

conducted on the efficient utilization of the existing teaching space facilities to validate this expansion.

Association of Physical Plant Administrators (APPA) Centre for Facilities Research (2012) report highlighted that tertiary institutions could address the issue of inadequate teaching space facilities by better utilizing their existing teaching facilities. The APPA report suggests that underutilized teaching space facilities can result in unnecessary institutional costs including energy and acoustic costs. According to Alghamdi (2018), a lack of strategic space planning in higher education institutions in Saudi Arabia resulted in the unnecessary construction of teaching space facilities across university campuses in the country. Therefore, to ensure more sustainable space provision and utilization, it is necessary to understand the dynamic of supply and demand for teaching space facilities on university campuses. It is, therefore, recommended that space management strategies such as utilization metrics and surveys should be implemented to address the space issue in the educational institutions (Alghamdi, 2018). The implication is that institutions should not just assume that their resources are insufficient, but instead, they should rigorously assess how they are using the resources (Ssempebwa et al., 2012).

Sheri-Offenhauser (2021) opined that a teaching space utilization survey is the best way to assess how much teaching space facilities are needed for teaching and learning in institutions. However, many tertiary institutions in Ghana lacks accurate data on the utilization level of their educational facilities including the teaching space facilities. To support this claim, the University Rationalization Committee Report (URC, 1988), as cited in Bosomtwe (2010), published that there is inadequate data on the utilization of educational facilities in Ghana's tertiary institutions, coupled with virtually a lack of guidelines, policies, and management strategies for their utilization. Therefore, educational planners and units in charge of facilities in tertiary institutions should consider implementing measures, such as conducting utilization surveys to accumulate data on utilization and keep track of how facilities are utilized in these institutions. This current study is of high relevance since it would help management to identify areas where the utilization of the teaching space facilities could be improved and highlight areas of good practice that could be adopted by other campuses. The outcomes of this study hold the potential to shape the formulation of impactful policies concerning the effective utilization of teaching spaces within the University campuses. Additionally, the findings would serve as the basis for the establishment of comprehensive policies governing teaching space allocation in tertiary institutions.

Research Question

These research questions guided the study:

1. What is the time, space, and global utilization rates of general-purpose lecture rooms at the University for Development Studies?
2. What measures can be taken to improve the utilization rates of teaching space facilities at University for Development Studies?

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

This study is underpinned by Facilities Management (FM) Theory and principles, which provides a strategic lens for analyzing the planning, usage, and improvement of

physical infrastructure within organizations. This theory is rooted in the works of prominent scholars such as Alexander (1996), Nutt (2000), and Atkin and Brooks (2000), the theory emphasizes the alignment of physical resources including teaching spaces with institutional goals, and the continuous assessment of their efficiency in utilization. In the context of this study, the FM Theory assumes that teaching space facilities such as lecture halls are vital assets that must be efficiently utilized to support quality education. It posits that optimal space utilization depends on systematic planning, measurable performance indicators such as occupancy rates, and responsive decision-making. Furthermore, the theory assumes that periodic evaluation and stakeholder engagement are essential to improving utilization rates of educational resource.

Practically, FM Theory aligns with this study by emphasizing the need to measure and monitor how teaching spaces are being used. The theory assumes that physical space is not merely a background resource but a strategic asset that can affect educational delivery. In this light, the theory supports the study's core objective which is to assess the efficiency of teaching space facilities and identify measures for improving their usage.

Utilization of Teaching Space

Utilization, in the context of this study, refers to the degree to which teaching spaces are effectively and efficiently used to support instructional activities. According to Louisiana Board of Regents (2003), space utilization is typically measured by comparing the actual use of teaching facilities to their availability or capacity. Efficient utilization implies that teaching spaces are appropriately allocated, scheduled, and maintained to meet academic needs. Several studies emphasize that optimal utilization of teaching space contributes significantly to educational quality and institutional efficiency. Quansah (2015) argues that poor space utilization leads to overcrowding, underuse of available infrastructure, and unnecessary expenditure on additional facilities. In contrast, effective space management ensures that available teaching spaces are matched with academic timetables, student enrolment patterns, and curriculum delivery strategies. In many developing countries, including Ghana, inadequate and uneven distribution of teaching spaces often hampers curriculum implementation. Large class sizes, coupled with insufficient lecture room infrastructure, lead to high pressure on available spaces, resulting in disrupted instructional time and reduced learner participation.

Metrics for Assessing Teaching Space Utilization Rate

There are three elementary measures to evaluate the utilization rates of teaching space facilities. These measures are the Time Utilization Rate (TUR), Space Utilization Rate (SUR), and Global Utilization Rate (GUR).

Time Utilization Rate (TUR), or Frequency of Use, records the proportion of time that a given space is occupied compared to its potential maximum time for usage. It is usually computed weekly, monthly, or yearly. The TUR is a significant metric employed in the evaluation of the productivity and effectiveness of the use of teaching facilities in universities. It is the proportion of time that a given instructional space is filled during a given period, taking into account both the time allocated for its potential use (theoretical number of hours) and usage time (actual number of hours used). The formula for calculating TUR is:

$$\text{TUR (\%)} = \frac{\text{Actual number of hours of use}}{\text{theoretical number of hours of use}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The Space Utilization Rate (SUR), also known as the Occupancy Rate, is a fundamental measure used to determine the efficiency of teaching space facilities. SUR calculates the ratio of the percentage of students who occupied a given lecture room within a defined period, to the maximum occupancy of the room and the duration the room was occupied. This ratio can be calculated weekly, monthly, or yearly (Rymarzak cited in Osei et al., 2024). This metric gives the proportion of space occupied over a defined period, taking into account both average occupied space (the average number of students available) and overall occupied space available for occupation (the actual student placement capacity available). This type of measurement offers valuable insight into the efficiency of teaching space utilization and identifies any potential inefficiencies in space utilization (Akinyemi, 2020).

To Calculate SUR, this formula is applied:

$$\text{SUR (\%)} = \frac{\text{Average number of students in attendance}}{\text{the actual number of students places available}} \times \quad (2)$$

The Global Utilization Rate (GUR) is a key measure that assesses the overall utilization of teaching spaces. It offers a comprehensive view of how efficient the teaching space is utilized. The calculation of GUR is derived from the product of two essential measures: the Time Utilization Rate (TUR) and the Space Utilization Rate (SUR). GUR is obtained by multiplying the TUR and SUR of a given teaching space. The TUR measures the proportion of time a teaching space is occupied over a specified period, while the SUR measures the proportion of space that is occupied during the same period.

GUR formula is:

$$\text{GUR (\%)} = \frac{\text{time utilization rate} \times \text{space utilization rate}}{100} \quad (3)$$

Standards for Assessing the Efficiency of Teaching Space Usage

Space utilization standards serve as essential tools for budgetary planning, enabling the assessment of the need for various academic spaces, such as lecture halls, laboratories, libraries, and faculty offices (California Postsecondary Education Commission, 2004). Table 1 provides utilization standards or benchmarks that help determine the efficiency of space utilization across different academic institutions worldwide.

Table 1. Institutional Standards for Assessing the Utilization Rates of Lecture Spaces

Institutions/systems	Year	Time utilization (%)	Space Utilization (%)	Global Utilization (%)
Washington System of Higher Education	1994	30	60	18

Arizona System of Higher Education	1997	30	60	18
University Rationalization Committee's Report	1988	80	66.7	53.4
North Carolina Higher Education	2000	35	65	23
UNC-Chapel Hill	2004	35	65	23
Utah System Higher Education	2010	34	66	22
South Carolina Commission Higher Ed.	2011	30	60	18
Florida Department Education	2014	40	60	24
University of Washington	2014	27	67	18
Cal State System (California Legislature)	2015	53	66	35
Colorado Higher Education	2015	30	67	20
HEWV Architects' Professional Expectations	2015	35	70	25
Rice University	2015	32	60	19
Kentucky Council Post-Secondary Ed.	2016	36	67	24
HEWV Architects' Professional Expectations	2016	33	67	22
University of California	2020	68	66	45

Table 1 shows an outline of utilization benchmarks by institutions for assessing efficiency of teaching space usage. Among these standards, the recommended standards by the University Rationalization Committees' (URC) 1988 is widely used in Ghanaian Universities to measure utilization rates of their teaching facilities. The URC analyzed teaching space utilization in Ghanaian universities and their assessment revealed a pervasive lack of standardization across institutions concerning the configuration and usage of lecture rooms, workshops, studios, and laboratories, as well as the provision of furniture and equipment. In response to this observed discrepancy, the committee proffered a solution to enhance the efficiency of teaching space utilization, the URC recommended the adoption of an 80%-time utilization rate. The University Rationalization Committee (URC) report stated that space utilization rate of 66.7% is deemed efficient, and a global utilization rate of less than 53.4% indicates an underutilization of teaching space facilities (Bosomtwe, 2010). This criterion was posited as a strategic metric to ensure a judicious and optimal use of university facilities. Subsequently, this standard has become integral for universities in Ghana, serving as a benchmark to assess the effectiveness of lecture room utilization, along with other critical facilities such as laboratories and libraries (Bosomtwe, 2010).

Measures to Improve Utilization Rate of Teaching Space Facilities

Literature on measures to improve the utilization level of teaching space facilities was reviewed from these perspectives: management-level measures that can be put in place to improve the utilization rates of teaching space facilities and measures that space users could take to improve the utilization rates of a teaching space facility.

Management-level Measures to Improve Utilization Rate of Teaching Space Facilities

The first measure to consider to improve teaching space utilization rates is management's effort to initiate an annual review of space utilization assessment (Alghamdi, 2018). An annual review of the teaching space utilization rates would provide valuable insight into the teaching space's usage. This will enable management to assess space utilization against the predefined benchmarks, guidelines, and standards. The review process can identify areas for improvement to optimize the use of teaching spaces and potentially reduce costs. Conducting an annual review of teaching space utilization rates can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of

the current utilization of the teaching spaces. This review would enable management of teaching institutions to evaluate the use of space against set benchmarks. The review process can highlight areas where improvements can be made to optimize the use of teaching spaces.

Students' enrolment decisions based on teaching spaces available and their capacity are among the measures that should be considered by management of educational institutions to improve teaching space utilization rates. Research has proven beyond doubt that students' enrolment affects the utilization rate of educational resources, which includes the teaching space facilities (Abdullah et al., 2012; Rahman et al., 2015; Akinyemi & Gbenu, 2020). This, therefore, implies that any management decision concerning students' enrolment would influence teaching space usage. Based on this assertion, Bosomtwe (2010) suggested that university and college management bodies should make admissions based on the seating capacities of the teaching spaces available. Another recommended measure proposed by Akinyemi and Gbenu (2020) was that the management in higher education should ensure the implementation of policies and guidelines about the specific number of students that every teaching space should contain, and the required dimension of the teaching space in tertiary institutions should be considered when planning on space allocations. Management should consider the maximum workload of lecturers to avoid overburdening them. This workload significantly influences their capacity to take on responsibilities, which can ultimately affect the overall utilization rate of teaching space facilities (Bosomtwe, 2010). Furthermore, Quansah (2015) emphasized the need for implementing high-level management policies to prevent academic staff from preferring specific times and days for lectures. It is suggested that academic staff should be mandated to strictly follow the timetable schedules assigned for their lectures. Moreover, the institutions' management, through the quality assurance process, should ensure that both lecturers and students adhere to the assigned lecture hours as outlined in the timetable for effective teaching and learning. This measure would aim to minimize or eliminate time losses during instruction for both students and lecturers (Akinyemi & Gbenu, 2020). This concern by Akinyemi and Gbenu (2020) boils down to supervision and monitoring of space usage, as proposed by Kolawole and Ogbiye (2020), that the government and leadership of schools should ensure utilization of educational resources, which include the teaching space facilities, through proper monitoring and supervision. With regards to timetabling and space allocation, management should organize time-to-time seminars or workshops for middle management who are responsible for timetable preparation at the university or college (Bosomtwe, 2010).

Allocation of teaching spaces (timetabling) is another critical aspect that space planners should emphasize. Several studies recommend the practice of centralized timetabling rather than departmentalized timetabling. However, these measures exclude specialized rooms since they lead to a rigid definition of teaching facilities within the confines of individual departments. (Quansah, 2015). In essence, more rooms should be accessible to all departments to increase the utilization rate of teaching space, and this can only be achieved when lecture rooms are managed centrally (Alghamdi, 2018). Even though decentralized timetabling has its advantages, many scholars who have researched in this area recommend the practice of centralized timetabling in schools since it is proven to be the best strategy to improve the utilization rates of a teaching facility (Owolabi, 1998; Baidoo, 2011; Bosomtwe, 2010; Abdullah et al., 2012; Quansah, 2015). Also, management should have an adequate database on students' enrolment into academic programmes and available teaching resources, including teaching space facilities, teaching materials, equipment, and furniture needs (University

Rationalization Report, 1988; Bosomtwe, 2010; Abdullah, 2012; Akinyemi & Gbenu, 2018). This information is necessary for the allocation of teaching spaces.

Baidoo (2011) proposed that as a means of keeping records, classes should be computerized based on class size, course requirements, teaching materials, equipment, and furniture needs. This will make the allocation of instructional rooms and their usage more efficient. Another measure from the management level that would improve the utilization rates of teaching space facilities is partitioning large multi-purpose classrooms with small classes. This partition should not be done with cement blocks so that it can serve not only small classes but also large classes when the need arises. Also, teaching spaces that are likely to be congested based on large-class size can be avoided by dividing the class size to accommodate the seating capacity or expanding the existing infrastructure to accommodate the ever-increasing student enrolment (Baidoo, 2011). Bosomtwe (2010) agreeably confirmed that splitting large class sizes into small class sizes would improve the time utilization rates of the teaching space facilities and also increase the use of the lecturer's time. Supportively, Baidoo (2011) and Quansah (2015) were of the view that large classrooms should be provided because it is necessary to provide large class sizes to ease congestion and to save teaching time and costs. However, instead of constructing permanent walls, it may be practical to partition overly spacious lecture rooms to serve dual functions. When partitioned, these rooms can accommodate smaller class sizes, and without the partition, they can be used for larger class sizes. Allocating teaching spaces for classes should be contingent on factors such as class size and specific course needs, including requirements for teaching materials, equipment, and furniture. According to Quansah (2015), if this is implemented, the instructional rooms will be used more often by different groups of learners based on their needs.

User-level Measures to improve utilization rates of Teaching Space Facilities

Numerous studies about the utilization of teaching space facilities have revealed that teaching space facilities record relatively low utilization rates during the afternoon and evening schools and sessions (Baidoo, 2011; Bosomtwe, 2010; Quansah, 2015). This inefficiency in the utilization rate happens as a result of human factors. Therefore, to mitigate or improve the utilization rates of the teaching facilities, space users (lecturers and students) should adhere strictly to the existing timetable, and lecturers must be implored to stick to the direction of the timetable. In addition to the measures needed to be taken by space users to improve teaching space utilization rates, space users must be dedicated to classroom teaching and learning. Moreso, academic staff must see to it that students are engaged around the clock and that intensive measures are taken to influence students to attend classes as scheduled (Baidoo, 2011).

Materials and Methods

Research Paradigm

The study was based on the pragmatist philosophy. Pragmatists have it that there is no single approach that can be deemed the best for all research problems, and instead, they believe that the most suitable approach depends on the nature of the problem, the questions being asked, and the researcher's resources and limitations (Feilzer, 2010; Johnson & Christensen, 2017).

In the context of the utilization of teaching space facilities, the pragmatist philosophy was highly fitting. The utilization of teaching space facilities is a complex and multi-

dimensional issue, and a thorough understanding of this issue would require data from multiple sources and perspectives. The pragmatist philosophy stresses the significance of tailoring the research methods to the specific requirements of the research problem. This means that the researcher would be able to choose the most suitable methods and approaches for the specific research questions being addressed.

Research Design

According to Creswell and Plano Clark (2018), a convergent parallel mixed-method design grounded in pragmatism philosophical assumptions is an effective and widely used approach in mixed-method research. Therefore, a convergent parallel mixed-method design was selected as the most appropriate design for the study because of its unique ability to collect and analyze both qualitative and quantitative data within a single study (Shorten & Smith, 2017).

The adopted convergent parallel mixed-method design primarily focused on conducting a comprehensive survey of the teaching space facilities. The survey, facilitated by an observation checklist, was carefully designed to gather quantitative data on various aspects of teaching space utilization, including frequency rates and occupancy rates. Concurrently, qualitative data was collected through interviews to provide an in-depth understanding of the measures to improve utilization rates of teaching space facilities. In this study, the researchers first analyzed and presented the quantitative data, followed by the qualitative data, in accordance with the research questions.

Research Approach

The study employed a mixed-method approach which combined qualitative and quantitative methods. The mixed method approach was used in the study as it was perceived to bring several advantages, including the ability to provide a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of a research problem and enable the researchers to gather both quantitative and qualitative data (Johnson & Christensen, 2017). Quantitative data offered numerical information that could be analyzed using statistical methods, while qualitative data provided more in-depth and descriptive information that gave deeper insights into participants view on measures for improving the utilization rates of teaching spaces.

Population

The population for this study consists of 9 academic administrators who are involved in matters relating to teaching space facilities within the institution, and 26 general-purpose lecture rooms available at UDS. These stakeholders comprise 7 faculty/school examination officers, and 2 estate officers. Due to the dynamic nature of academic administration roles and the difficulty in getting a precise number for the entire population, the inclusion criterion was based on the importance of roles in matters related to teaching space facilities. Since the primary focus of the study was to assess the utilization of teaching space facilities, specifically general-purpose lecture rooms, these rooms formed part of the study population. This is in line with the premise that the study population, as quoted in literature, does not necessarily point to human beings but could be inclusive of any variables that a researcher would want to investigate (Bhandari, 2020). Hence, the decision to incorporate general-purpose lecture rooms in the study population was warranted. The university had at its disposal 26 general-purpose lecture rooms (Field survey, 2024), all of which were selected as subject targets for the study.

Sampling and Sampling Technique

The study used a sample size of 35 which constitutes 9 academic administrators, and 26 general-purpose lecture rooms. A purposive sampling technique was utilized to select the nine (9) academic administrators for the interview, they include; seven (7) faculty examination officers, and two (2) estate officers. The academic administrators were purposively selected because they were in charge of the timetabling and the day-to-day management and maintenance of the physical teaching space facilities in the university. Interviewing them to gather their opinions on the utilization of the teaching spaces and proper management systems that would bring about efficiency in utilization at the University for Development Studies was deemed appropriate. The sample size for the interview was considered enough for the study because interviewing many people with similar qualities would provide a restricted number of opinions since certain opinions would be repeated over and over (Cober & Adams, 2020). To support this, Hennink and Kaiser (2022) opined that qualitative studies often reach data saturation with an interview range of 9 to 17. Therefore, having a sample size of 9 participants for the interview is considered appropriate.

On the space facilities at the UDS-Tamale Campus, all general-purpose teaching space facilities were selected for the study through the census sampling technique. As of the time of the study, the campus had 26 general-purpose lecture rooms, and all were assessed for the utilization study. These facilities were selected because they are the facilities that are assigned for general lectures.

Research Instruments

This study employed two separate instruments to gather data, aiming for a comprehensive exploration of the teaching space utilization at the University for Development Studies, Tamale Campus. These instruments included an observation checklist, and an interview guide.

The observation checklist was used to gather the quantitative data on the general-purpose lecture rooms for the study while the interview guide was used to gather the qualitative data for the study. The checklist was adapted from Quansah (2007) study and modified to suit the existing conditions of UDS-Tamale Campus since the structures, sizes, seating capacities of general-purpose lecture rooms, and timetabling differs from one institution to the other. UDS-Tamale campus had 6 blocks and these blocks contained 26 general-purpose lecture rooms. Therefore, the observation checklist was designed in six sections, labelled A to F, each of these sections was used to observe a block. The sections had similar items to check, these included the area in square meters, seating capacity, the actual time for the lesson, starting time, end time, and number of students present for class. The researchers, together with the trained research assistants, observed these items and recorded the findings systematically in the observation checklist.

In this study, the researchers personally designed a semi-structured interview to collect data from the academic administrators. A semi-structured interview was used because this type of interview allowed for follow-up questions to be asked depending on the participant's experiences and views on the issues under study (Utibe, 2020). The purpose of employing this instrument was to elicit the opinions of academic administrators on the measures to improve the utilization rates of teaching space facilities at the UDS-Tamale Campus. The interview instrument was in one (1) section. The section contained five questions. The topic covered in the section was measures to improve utilization of a teaching space facility.

Reliability and Validity

The principles of reliability and validity were used to assess the quality of this research. Reliability and validity demonstrate the accuracy and consistency of a research method, technique, and instrumentation. The observation checklist was pilot tested for weeks using general-purpose lecture rooms at the UDS-Nyankpala Campus to ascertain whether the instrument would achieve what is meant to achieve. The interview instrument was also pre-tested on some faculty examination officers from the Nyankpala Campus. These participants were selected for the pre-test because of the familiarity they have concerning teaching space usage. The researchers engaged them based on the reason that they work hand-in-hand with the campus examination officer, the faculty examination officers on the Tamale campus and sometimes the estate officers. Therefore, they would be privy to issues about the use of the teaching spaces available to the University. Also, since the faculty examination officers in the Nyankpala campus were not included in the actual study, conducting a pilot testing with them was apt. The pre-test of the instrument was carried out at the participant's convenience to make sure that the validity of the instruments was achieved (Majid et al, 2017).

Since the study made use of a semi-structured interview, the researchers invariably fixed questions that measured the same construct, and responses to these two questions were compared to see the consistency in participants' responses. Having compared participants' responses to those questions it was realized that there was a kind of consistency in their responses, which indicated that the outcome of the research was trustworthy.

The integration of the two research methods (mixed-method) in the study increased the confidence that the findings and conclusions of this study is valid and reliable since the approach allowed the researchers to use a combination of different data; that is data from observation, and interview to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the complex issues (Poth & Munce, 2020).

Data Collection Procedure

To initiate the study, an introductory letter was obtained from the Head of the Department, seeking permission from the University Management to conduct the research at UDS. Deans of various Schools were informed about engaging their examination officers in the study. Individual letters were then distributed to examination officers, and estate officers requesting their participation in the study. The purpose of the research was explained to the participants, and their consent was obtained before involving them in the data collection process. Twenty-six general-purpose lecture rooms' floor spaces within the six lecture blocks, that is the Faculty of Education Block, the Library Block, the New Block, the School of Medicine and Health Sciences Block, the School of Allied Health Sciences Block, and the Multi-purpose Auditorium were measured with a tape measure to determine their actual square footage. This measurement was essential for calculating the capacity and the space utilization rates of the general-purpose lecture rooms.

Having trained the research assistants on how to gather the data using the observation checklist, the researchers together with the research assistants observed the lecture rooms for a total of eight weeks within the 2023/2024 academic year, with four weeks in the first trimester and four weeks in the second trimester. The observation began three weeks after the beginning of the first and second trimesters and ended four weeks before the commencement of student's examination. The 26 general-purpose lecture

rooms were observed from Monday to Friday, 7:00am to 7:00pm as prescribed on the timetable.

A face-to-face interview was scheduled with the academic administrators to gather the qualitative data for the study. An audio tape recorder was used to record the interview but the researchers sought permission from respondents before taking the voice recording. The audiotape facilitated accurate transcription. Each of the interviews lasted for not less than 30 minutes and at most 50 minutes.

Ethical Consideration

In this study, ethical issues were considered. The researchers sought permission from the University Management and individual participants who took part in the study to respond candidly to the instruments. This was done because it was deemed necessary and appropriate for the researchers to engage with participants in a professional way but not in an exploitative or aggressive manner. The research team maintained a respectful, attentive, and responsive approach to participants' needs and concerns. Participants who volunteered to participate in the study had the opportunity to quit at any time they felt disinterested. Participants were urged to give honest responses to the questions and were also assured of keeping their opinions confidential. The secrecy, privacy, and anonymity of all participants were carefully valued. To ensure these, the researchers made sure that any data collected was in a way that did not violate participants' privacy and confidentiality. Also, the researchers securely stored the data and used codes instead of participants' names or identifying information. Participants were made aware of any recordings made and were given the option to decline participation in the recording. The research assistants who assisted in gathering data with the observation checklist were educated to adhere to ethics in gathering data.

Data Analysis

The researchers separately analyzed the data collected using both quantitative descriptive and thematic analysis techniques. The quantitative data gathered through the observation checklist were descriptively analyzed using the standard metrics for assessing teaching space utilization rates (Equations 1, 2, and 3). To begin with, the researchers needed to determine the actual number of student places available (room capacity). The researchers adopted the Louisiana Board of Regent (2003) formula to determine the capacity of each of the general-purpose lecture spaces available at UDS. The formula involves dividing the total assignable square meters by the square meters per student station to determine the capacity of an instructional room.

Mathematically,

$$\text{Room Capacity} = \frac{\text{Total assignable square meter}}{\text{Square meter per student station}} \quad (4)$$

The researchers measured each general-purpose lecture space to determine its square meter and then used the University Rationalization Committee's (URC) report (1988) recommended norm of 1.84 square meters (19.8 square feet) per student station to perform the calculation. The URC norm was used because of its wide recognition for assessing teaching spaces at universities in Ghana. The researchers computed the Time Utilization Rates (TUR), Space Utilization Rates (SUR), and Global Utilization Rates (GUR). The utilization rates (TUR, SUR, and GUR) were used as indicators to compare with the University Rationalization Committee's (1988) recommended

standard for efficient utilization, which is 80.0% for TUR, 66.7% for SUR, and 53.4% for GUR.

Qualitative analysis was conducted on the interview responses. An inductive bottom-up thematic analysis technique was used for this analysis. The researchers familiarized themselves with the data, produced codes, searched for themes among the codes generated, examined the themes discovered from the codes, defined and labelled the themes, and generated the findings in a report. The adaptation of these processes began by transcribing the recorded responses to familiarize the researchers with the data obtained. The transcribed data was read and coded frequently to ensure it reflected the data.

Results and Discussion

The results and discussion of this study focus on calculating the Time Utilization Rate (TUR), Space Utilization Rate (SUR), and Global Utilization Rate (GUR) for general-purpose lecture halls from Monday to Friday during the first and second trimesters of the 2023/2024 academic year, along with themes that came up in the interviews. A checklist was used throughout the eight-week observation period to identify trends in teaching space usage, thereby supplying indispensable information for subsequent analysis through the use of utilization measures. Time Utilization Rate, Space Utilization Rate, and Global Utilization Rate patterns were constructed for all general-purpose lecture halls in morning sessions (7:00 am - 11:00 am), afternoon sessions (11:00 am – 3:00 pm), and evening sessions (3:00 pm - 7:00 pm) on Mondays to Fridays during the first and second trimesters of the 2023/2024 academic year. An interview guide was used to gather the qualitative data for the thematic analysis and discussions on the measures to improve the utilization rates.

Research Question 1: What is the time, space, and global utilization rates of general-purpose lecture rooms at the University for Development Studies?

Research question one sought to assess the rates at which the general-purpose lecture rooms available at UDS was being utilized. The utilization assessment was done using the standard metrics for calculating the time utilization rate (TUR), space utilization rate (SUR), and global utilization rate (GUR). (refer to equation 1, 2, and 3 respectively). The rates recorded from the assessment for the trimesters and the whole academic year were benchmarked with the standard threshold for efficient utilization on general-purpose lecture spaces which is, 80.0% for TUR, 66.7% for SUR, and 53.4% for GUR as recommended in the University Rationalization Committees' (1988) report.

Table 2 (Appendix) presents the average utilization rates of the teaching space facilities, specifically the general-purpose lecture rooms for the first and second trimesters as well as the whole academic year (2023/2024). The utilization rates thus the TURs, SURs, and GURs were obtained from each of the general-purpose lecture halls available at the UDS-Tamale campus. The researchers summed up the various utilization rates of each of the general-purpose lecture spaces and averaged them to derive the rates seen in the Table 2. This computation was done for each of the trimesters. Also, the TURs, SURs, and GURs of both trimesters were summed up to derive the average for the whole academic year rates.

As evident from Table 2 (Appendix), the general-purpose lecture spaces available at UDS-Tamale campus recorded the highest TUR rate in the first trimester as compared

to the second trimester. A high TUR of 52.8% was recorded in the first trimester and 38.2% TUR for the second trimester. Similarly, to the SUR, the first trimester had the highest rate of 84.1% indicating efficient usage of the general-purpose teaching spaces available at UDS as the SUR value is above the recommended rate of 66.7% (URC, 1988). The second trimester recorded (63.1%) of the target rate for efficiency indicating that the general-purpose lecture spaces were not optimally utilized. The GUR also followed a similar trend where the first trimester recorded the highest rate compared to the second trimester. The trimesters had 50.6% and 31.3% GUR respectively. These values indicate that the general-purpose lecture spaces were not efficiently utilized by students if juxtaposed to the target GUR of 53.4% as recommended by the UCR (1988). Generally, the overall TUR, SUR, and GUR for all general-purpose lecture rooms were relatively higher in the first trimester than in the second trimester. These relatively low rates in the second trimester of the academic year would partly be that the majority of the courses are mounted in the first trimester and few courses in the second trimester.

Analyzing the utilization rates obtained for the whole academic year (2023/2024), the TUR of 46.1% for the 26 general-purpose lecture spaces was far lower than the target rate of 80% for efficient time utilization set by the University Rationalization Committee (1988) the instructional periods assigned for the lecture spaces were not optimally utilized. This finding correlates with the assertion by Kenny and Foster as cited in Bosomtwe (2010), Quansah (2015), and Baidoo (2011) that 80% TUR is impractical and further stated that even with the utilization of computerized time scheduling and space allocation, achieving such a rate would be unfeasible. A higher SUR of 73.8% was recorded for the whole academic year signalling that the lecture rooms were efficiently utilized since the rate derived from this study is significantly higher than the target rate (66.7%) for optimal utilization of a teaching space (URC, 1988). The study recorded an observed GUR of 41.5% this indicates that the lecture spaces were underutilized as compared to the URC (1988) rate of 53.4%. The observed GUR is below the target rate which implies that the lecture rooms were underutilized since the URC report stipulates that a less than 53.4% GUR is an indication of underutilization. However, this global utilization rate can be seen as an improvement when compared to the utilization rates at UG and UCC, UEW which are 20.6%, 16.0%, and 38.9% respectively (Owolabi, 1993 as cited in Quansah, 2015), and the utilization rate at Takoradi Polytechnic, documented as 51.4% by Akomaning (2001). This finding affirms Owolabi's comparative analysis of teaching space utilization in Higher Education Institutions in Ghana, highlighting that Polytechnics generally exhibit higher utilization rates than universities.

Table 2 (Appendix) also indicates that general-purpose lecture spaces exhibited relatively high utilization rates on Mondays compared to other days, with a TUR of 51.6%, SUR of 83.4%, and GUR of 51.1%. Tuesdays saw rates of 50.2%, 76.5%, and 45.9% for TUR, SUR, and GUR, respectively. Wednesdays also showed notable values of 46.4%, 72.1%, and 39.2% for TUR, SUR, and GUR. Thursdays recorded rates of 43.1%, 68.8%, and 39.7% for TUR, SUR, and GUR. Fridays, on the other hand, had the lowest rates of 39.3%, 68.2%, and 31.6% for TUR, SUR, and GUR, respectively. The observed low TUR, SUR, and GUR on Fridays can be attributed to the unique scheduling challenges arising from the university's geographic location, where the predominant religion is Islam. Fridays are designated for Jumu'ah prayers in the afternoon, a significant religious activity. Although the university's academic timetable is not directly influenced by this religious practice, the cultural context prompts lecturers to allow students time for prayer and, in some cases, leads to the cancellation

of lectures. As a result, the interruption to regular academic activities on Fridays partly contributes to the lower TUR, and SUR on this particular day. Another contributing factor to this low TUR, SUR, and GUR on Fridays could be teacher apathy towards conducting lectures on Fridays. Some lecturers perceive Fridays as the beginning of their weekend, leading to a potential lack of enthusiasm or commitment to teach on this day, and this attitude could influence the overall student attendance and engagement during Friday lectures. This finding is in line with Baidoo's (2011) study, which revealed low utilization trends on Fridays as a result of lecturers' apathy to lecture on Fridays as they see Fridays to begin their weekend.

In summary, Mondays consistently demonstrated high utilization rates for general-purpose lecture rooms, while Fridays consistently recorded lower utilization rates for these spaces.

Research Question 2: What measures can be taken to improve the utilization of teaching space facilities at UDS?

This research question aimed to explore participants' perspectives on measures to improve the utilization rates of teaching space facilities, particularly general-purpose lecture rooms at UDS. From the interview transcriptions, three main thematic categories and three sub-themes emerged for discussion. These thematic categories and sub-themes are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Thematic Categories and Sub-themes Emerged from the Interview Excerpts

Thematic categories	Sub-themes
Promoting a Culture of Responsibility	Punctuality and Regular Attendance
Addressing Inadequate Teaching Spaces	Expansion of lecture facilities
Strategic Planning for Efficient Utilization	Proper Planning and Coordination of Space Allocation

Promoting a Culture of Responsibility to Improve Utilization Rates

When exploring measures to enhance the utilization rates of available teaching space facilities, particularly in the general-purpose lecture rooms at the Tamale Campus, a prevalent theme surfaced as "Promotion of a Culture of Responsibility" as a thematic category. Punctuality and Regular Attendance emerge as sub-theme under this thematic category for discussion as pivotal measures for optimizing the efficiency of teaching spaces.

Punctuality and Regular Attendance

Participants proposed that fostering a sense of responsibility among both students and lecturers would have influence on the utilization rates of the teaching facilities. This involves punctuality and regular attendance of lectures, and ensuring that lectures commence and conclude precisely within the allocated time as specified on the timetable. For efficient utilization of the teaching space, participants suggested that:

The first one or the broader one is discipline in the case of lecturers and also with the students. Discipline in the sense that the space users that is the students and lecturers come to lectures on time and close on time because normally when you are done a different lecturer comes in so if you do not honor the instructional time, it would affect the academic work and the utilization

rates. Also, I will say punctuality is key. If we want to improve the utilization rates of our lecture spaces lecturers and students must be punctual to lectures because cancelling of lectures and lateness to lectures affect the utilization rates. – (Exam Officer 4)

Yes, I agree with that. Discipline and punctuality are very important when it comes to using lecture spaces effectively. If students and lecturers do not come on time or fail to close on time, it creates problems for the next users of the space. Sometimes, one class delays and it affects the whole schedule. Also, when lectures are cancelled or start late, it reduces the proper use of the space. So, to improve how well we use our lecture spaces, both lecturers and students must take time management seriously. – (Exam Officer 7)

The quotation from the participants underscores the importance of punctuality to lectures for effective lecture space utilization. From the participant's view point, both students and lecturers must adhere to schedule instructional times to avoid disruptions in academic work and maintain optimal utilization rates. Punctuality is identified as a key factor influencing the efficient utilization rates of general-purpose lecture spaces, with the participant emphasizing the need for timely attendance to enhance overall utilization rates.

Addressing Inadequate Teaching Spaces

Addressing inadequate teaching spaces surfaced as the second thematic category under this research question. In exploring measures to enhance the utilization of teaching spaces, particularly within the general-purpose lecture rooms at the Tamale campus of UDS, one significant consideration that surfaced as a sub-theme under the thematic category 2 is the expansion of lecture facilities. Participants emphasized the need for larger lecture halls to effectively accommodate large class sizes to improve overall space utilization.

Expansion of Lecture Facilities

Participants revealed that, to enhance time and space utilization rates, there is a need for management to construct additional lecture spaces, specifically large halls. Participants further argue that inefficiencies in teaching space usage result from inadequate teaching facilities on Tamale Campus of the university. They also suggest that inadequate lecture rooms resulted in the extension of lecture hours from 7 am to 7 pm instead of the previous hours of 8 am to 5 pm. Therefore, increasing the number of teaching space facilities would prevent the over-utilization of space. The participants mentioned that:

I believe the primary issue is management making provisions for establishing additional lecture room facilities, especially larger halls as many of our current lecture rooms cannot accommodate large class sizes. I believe most of these inefficiencies in the teaching space usage are a result of inadequate teaching spaces so we are all struggling to get the space, at times as a result some of these things happen because for example, previously lectures end at 5 pm but because of space they have to extend it to 7 pm and some members argue that it is overtime they are doing since their appointment spells out that they are not supposed to work at 5 pm. Because of this, if you assign someone for that evening lecture it is not mandatory since the person can choose to meet the students or not. - (Exam Officer 2)

For now, with our current situation, we have reached our saturation point and the best option is to get more lecture halls. I say this because you observe that it is not enough and now we have a growing department where there are students just in level 100 some level 200 some up to level 300 now when we look at some departments we only have up to level 300 so next academic year we will be having 400 which means another set of students will be joining the numbers

which mean the existing number is not going to be the same, new programmes are coming on board, other departments have growing population and we are already saturated. This simply means that we need more resources so the best and safest way to solve the future congestion in lecture halls is to get more lecture halls and furniture. So we need space because when the furniture comes we need it, even the furniture we have is not enough already, we will need furniture but the pressing need is space because if the furniture comes now where are we going to put it even though some of the rooms the furniture are not enough but when you full them, student will still hang for example TF7 we find student on the corridor to the stairs some come for lectures and sit on the stairs so we just need spaces.- (Exam Officer 3)

It is a multi-facilities problem so we need a multi-solution to solve it but I think that the main issue is for us to get more lecture spaces if we get more lecture spaces it would work because lectures will begin early. Also, getting an orientation for students; initially, we were not having lectures that early with classes we used to have lectures around 8 which was more comfortable because some of the students were coming from town and far from the campus. (Estate Officer 2)

From the quotations, participants collectively highlight a pressing concern regarding the insufficiency of current lecture room facilities on Tamale campus. One participant points out the repercussions of this inadequacy, revealing that facility planners are compelled to extend lecture hours beyond the designated period. This extension triggers debates over overtime work, affecting the commitment of lecturers to evening classes. Another participant emphasizes that a saturation point has been reached in the available lecture halls. Anticipating a surge in student enrolment and the introduction of new programmes puts pressure on the existing inadequate teaching space facilities in the institution. The urgent call for additional lecture halls and furniture is amplified, citing congestion in existing spaces where students resort to sitting on stairs due to limited seats.

A multi-faceted solution is proposed by another participant to address the challenges. Acquiring more lecture spaces is deemed crucial, with the expectation that it would facilitate the early commencement of lectures. Additionally, the participant advocates for student orientation to encourage early attendance, referencing past practices where classes started around 8 a.m. for commuting students' convenience. This recommendation aligns with the findings and recommendations of Baidoo (2011) and Quansah et al. (2024) that the issue of overcapacity arises from insufficiently sized instructional rooms and could be addressed by providing more facilities to accommodate the substantial number of students.

Strategic Planning for Efficient Utilization

Under the main theme of 'Strategic Planning for Efficient Utilization,' participants emphasized the importance of stakeholders' involvement and extensive consultations. This approach aims to collectively identify positive practices and strategies to enhance the efficient utilization of teaching spaces at UDS.

Proper Planning and Coordination of Space Allocation

Participants also recorded that for the institution to achieve efficient utilization of its teaching spaces, there should be proper planning and coordination of space allocations. This involves taking note of practical lessons outside the general-purpose lecture rooms so that those spaces can be utilized during that period. Participants suggested that:

I suggest that courses that would have practical lessons outside the lecture space should be taken notice of by the space managers when allocating the spaces, so that they can schedule lectures at those spaces during that time. I think the various course lecturers can give prior notice on that to aid the exam officers in scheduling lectures during that time. – (Estate Officer 1)

I propose that we give attention to courses with practical elements that would be conducted outside regular lecture halls when making the allocation of the spaces as against the courses. This would allow the release of those lecture halls that would be vacant for other course during those practical times. I suggest that course lecturers should provide notice of their practical sessions outside the lecture hall in advance to allow the examination officers to schedule an effective lecture timetable – (Exam Officer 6)

Another participant also mentioned that:

Yes, as I said earlier, there should be a plan for the utilization of the facilities, we should have a plan as to how to go by using the available lecture spaces. If we do not plan well, we are bound to fail, as the saying goes failing to plan is planning to fail. This plan involves careful consideration of factors such as scheduling, coordination, and the specific needs of various courses. – (Exam Officer 5)

The quotation reveals that participants suggested proper planning and coordination of lecture room allocation. This entails taking note of courses with practical lessons outside the general-purpose lecture space for reallocation of the lecture rooms when not in use to improve the utilization rates of the lecture rooms. This aligns with the findings of Bosomtwe (2010), and Quansah (2015) that low utilization rates are often attributed to activities outside the lecture rooms. The participants recommended effective planning and coordination as essential measures to improve utilization rates.

Summary of Findings

1. The study revealed that the Ghana Tertiary Education Commission (GTEC) has not published any standards or guidelines for space per student occupancy, which can serve as a benchmark for tertiary institutions in Ghana to determine the seating capacities of their teaching space facilities. The absence of clear benchmarks contributes to overcrowding-related discomfort and distractions in lecture rooms, directly resulting in risks during emergency evacuations and compromising students' health conditions.
2. The study revealed that the average Time Utilization Rates (TUR) of all 26 general-purpose lecture rooms was low at 46.1%, indicating a trend of underutilization. The 46.1% TUR for the academic year is far below the target rate of 80% for optimal time utilization, as stated by the University Rationalization Committee (URC) in 1988.
3. The study disclosed that the university's general-purpose lecture halls had an efficient Space Utilization Rate (SUR) of 73.8% for the academic year, meaning efficient use. The proportion is far better than the 66.7% set standards for efficiency in the use of teaching space facilities by URC (1988).
4. An average Global Utilization Rate (GUR) of 41.5% for general-purpose lecture rooms at UDS was achieved indicating underutilization of the lecture facility. The GUR of 41.5% was compared to the URC (1988) rate of 53.4% and is below the target rates for the teaching space facility to be optimally utilized.
5. The study found that University for Development Studies general-purpose lecture rooms were most used on Mondays among other school days, with the lowest

usage being on Fridays. The Mondays recorded a GUR of 51.1%, which was lower than the URC (1988) benchmarked requirement of 53.4%. Fridays, on the contrary, registered very low levels of usage, with an average of GUR standing at 31.6%.

6. The research also revealed that, morning sessions recorded the highest utilization rates for all general-purpose lecture rooms with a GUR of 65.2%, well above the target rate established by the URC (1988) at 53.4%. This shows that general-purpose lecture rooms were intensively used during morning sessions.

7. The study also revealed several strategic measures towards improving teaching space utilization rates in the University for Development Studies. These strategic measures include promoting a culture of responsibility among lecturers and students. The participants stressed that regular attendance and punctuality are required in ensuring that lecture rooms are efficiently utilized. Delay in lecture beginnings or endings tend to create disruptions in the lecture schedule, thus impacting the smooth conduct of classes and minimizing the overall usefulness of the teaching space available.

8. The study further revealed the need to address the inadequacy of existing teaching spaces. A significant number of participants remarked that the current facilities are not sufficient to take in the growing number of students. As a result, the expansion of lecture halls either by construction of new buildings or renovation of existing ones was suggested as a necessary measure towards alleviating congestion and improving the utilization rates of the general-purpose lecture spaces.

9. Finally, the study highlighted the role of proper planning and coordination in achieving efficient space utilization. Participants noted that ineffective scheduling and communication among space managers normally result in underutilization of lecture spaces. Strategic planning, including early communication from lecturers about practical sessions held outside the lecture room, was suggested as a way to better align course requirements with available space. Involving academic staff in the scheduling process was also seen as a way to improve coordination and avoid conflicts in space allocation.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the lack of published standards or guidelines by the Ghana Tertiary Education Commission (GTEC) on space per student occupancy presents a significant gap in the regulation of teaching space management across tertiary institutions in Ghana. This absence of clear benchmarks makes it difficult for universities to determine optimal seating capacities for lecture facilities.

It is further concluded that the general-purpose lecture rooms at the University for Development Studies (UDS) are underutilized, as evidenced by a low Teaching Utilization Rate (TUR) of 46.1% and an average Global Utilization Rate (GUR) of 41.5%. Although the available spaces were used effectively when occupied, the overall utilization rate remained below acceptable levels, indicating inefficiencies in space usage.

The study also concludes that space usage at UDS is unevenly distributed across the week, with peak usage occurring on Mondays and the lowest on Fridays. In addition, morning sessions recorded the highest utilization rates, suggesting that scheduling

practices do not fully maximize the potential use of lecture facilities throughout the day and week.

Moreover, the study concludes that certain strategic measures are necessary to improve the utilization of teaching spaces. These include promoting a culture of punctuality and regular attendance among both students and lecturers to minimize disruptions and improve the smooth turnover of lecture sessions. The study further concludes that the current lecture space infrastructure is inadequate for the increasing student population, making expansion or renovation of existing facilities essential.

Finally, it is concluded that poor planning and coordination significantly affect space utilization. Ineffective scheduling and limited communication among stakeholders lead to underuse and conflicts in space allocation. Involving academic staff in scheduling decisions and ensuring timely communication about course-specific needs, especially those requiring practical out-side lecture hall, were identified as key strategies to enhance teaching space management.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made to improve the utilization of teaching space facilities at the University for Development Studies (UDS) and similar institutions:

Firstly, it is recommended that the Ghana Tertiary Education Commission (GTEC) develop and publish standardized guidelines for space per student occupancy. These guidelines will serve as a benchmark for tertiary institutions across Ghana, enabling them to assess and plan their teaching space capacities in a more structured and efficient manner. Having such guidelines in place will help ensure that teaching spaces are appropriately sized for student populations, thus preventing both overcrowding and underutilization of resources.

In addition, it is essential for UDS and other universities to implement regular monitoring and evaluation of their Time Utilization Rates (TUR), Space Utilization Rate (SUR) and Global Utilization Rates (GUR). Conducting periodic assessments on the utilization rates of teaching facilities would help universities to identify patterns of space usage and make informed decisions about optimizing space usage. This will also allow for better resource allocation, ensuring that teaching spaces are maximally utilized at all times.

The study further recommends that UDS revise its academic timetables to ensure a more even distribution of classes. Additionally, Friday afternoons, which recorded lower utilization rates, should be considered for class scheduling to maximize the potential use of available spaces.

Furthermore, it is recommended that the university promote a culture of punctuality and regular attendance among both students and lecturers. This can be achieved by introducing policies that encourage adherence to scheduled times and discouraging late arrivals and early departures. Punctuality can also be integrated into the performance evaluation of staff and students, making it a key factor in ensuring effective space utilization.

Moreover, addressing the inadequacy of current teaching space facilities specifically the general-purpose lecture rooms is another critical recommendation. As the study revealed, the growing student population at UDS requires additional facilities to

prevent overcrowding and ensure adequate space for all students. Therefore, the university should prioritize the expansion of lecture facilities, whether through the construction of new lecture halls or the renovation of existing ones. This expansion will provide sufficient room for students and prevent the strain on already overburdened spaces.

Finally, it is recommended that UDS establish better coordination between departments and stakeholders who manage the teaching spaces to ensure that teaching spaces are allocated efficiently. Early communication from lecturers about practical sessions held outside the lecture room can help avoid scheduling conflicts and improve the overall planning process.

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Conflict of Interests

There is no conflict of interest.

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Appendix

Table 2. Average Utilization Rates of All General-purpose Lecture Rooms Available at University for Development Studies for 2023/2024 Academic Year

Day	Period	1 st Trimester			2 nd Trimester			Whole Academic Year		
		TUR	SUR	GUR	TUR	SUR	GUR	TUR	SUR	GUR
Monday	7 am-11 am	74.2%	135.8%	103.5%	56.8%	83.4%	56.5%	65.5%	109.6%	80.1%
	11 am-3 pm	58.6%	101.5%	62.4%	46.1%	67.8%	35.6%	52.4%	84.7%	49.0%
	3 pm-7 pm	41.7%	59.9%	27.1%	32.2%	51.9%	21.2%	36.9%	55.9%	24.2%
	Whole day	58.2%	99.1%	64.3%	45.0%	67.7%	37.8%	51.6%	83.4%	51.1%
Tuesday	7 am-11 am	74.3%	114.1%	88.0%	57.0%	86.2%	50.9%	65.7%	100.2%	72.7%
	11 am-3 pm	55.7%	91.4%	55.3%	42.3%	63.5%	28.5%	49.1%	77.5%	42.0%
	3 pm-7 pm	41.2%	62.5%	28.1%	30.6%	41.3%	17.9%	35.9%	51.8%	23.0%
	Whole day	57.1%	89.3%	57.1%	43.3%	63.7%	32.4%	50.2%	76.5%	45.9%
Wednesday	7 am-11 am	70.5%	114.8%	86.1%	48.7%	75.7%	30.1%	59.7%	95.3%	58.4%
	11 am-3 pm	54.2%	87.3%	51.5%	44.9%	63.5%	32.3%	49.6%	75.4%	41.9%
	3 pm-7 pm	38.0%	58.5%	25.3%	21.6%	32.4%	9.3%	29.9%	45.5%	17.4%
	Whole day	54.2%	86.9%	54.3%	38.4%	57.2%	23.9%	46.4%	72.1%	39.2%
Thursday	7 am-11 am	66.8%	109.9%	70.6%	39.9%	73.9%	41.7%	54.8%	91.9%	59.3%
	11 am-3 pm	53.5%	76.0%	43.3%	39.3%	62.3%	40.9%	46.5%	69.2%	42.1%
	3 pm-7 pm	37.4%	50.0%	20.7%	18.8%	40.4%	14.7%	28.1%	45.3%	17.7%
	Whole day	52.6%	78.6%	44.9%	32.7%	58.9%	32.4%	43.1%	68.8%	39.7%
Friday	7 am-11 am	55.8%	94.7%	56.7%	46.7%	90.5%	53.9%	51.3%	92.6%	55.3%
	11 am-3 pm	38.7%	62.8%	25.6%	28.0%	72.5%	26.9%	33.4%	67.6%	26.3%
	3 pm-7 pm	30.6%	42.6%	15.1%	20.4%	40.9%	11.2%	33.3%	44.5%	13.2%
	Whole day	41.7%	66.7%	32.5%	31.7%	68.0%	30.1%	39.3%	68.2%	31.6%
Overall		52.8%	84.1%	50.6%	38.2%	63.1%	31.3%	46.1%	73.8%	41.5%

Source: Field Survey (2023)

